

ACTIVITY 2.2.2.3: SITE SELECTION REPORT

A Report from STOP Spillover Cambodia

December 2023

Bat guano harvesters at Phnom Kuhear Loung's bat cave bringing down their harvest.

(Photo Credit: STOP Spillover Cambodia)

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STOP SPILLOVER

Strategies to Prevent Spillover (or “STOP Spillover”) enhances global understanding of the complex causes of the spread of a selected group of zoonotic viruses from animals to humans. The project builds government and stakeholder capacity in priority Asian and African countries to identify, assess, and monitor risks associated with these viruses and develop and introduce proven risk reduction measures. “Spillover” refers to an event in which an emerging zoonotic virus is transferred from a non-human animal host species (livestock or wildlife) to another, or to humans.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

BTB	Battambang
CDC	Cambodia Disease Controls
CIFs	Community Investment Funds
FA	Forestry Administration
FGD	Focused Group Discussion
FIG	Figure
GDAHP	General Department of Animal Health and Production
GOC	Government of Cambodia
HC	Health Center
INGO	International Non-governmental Organization
KII	Key Informant Interview
NGO	Non-governmental Organization
NIRA	National Interface Risk Assessment
NiV	Nipah Virus
OD	Operational District
OH-DReaM WG	One Health for Designed Research and Mentoring Working Group
PDAFF	Provincial Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries
PDOE	Provincial Department of Environment
PDOME	Provincial Department of Mine and Energy
PDH	Provincial Department of Health
PKLFPC	Phnom Kuhear Loung Forestry Protection Community
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
PRSFPC	Phnom Rumsay Sak Forestry Protection Community
RT-PCR	Reverse Transcription Polymerase Chain Reaction
SARS-COV-2	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2
STOP	Strategies to Prevent
ToT	Training of Trainers

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In Cambodia, cave-dwelling bats are suspected to host zoonotic coronaviruses with potential pandemic risk. The practice of collecting bat guano for fertilizer increases the risk of viral spillover at the bat-human interface, as people come into direct contact with the guano or urine via respiratory, mucous membrane and cutaneous routes. To address these risks, STOP Spillover is developing interventions targeting cave-associated bat-human interface sites in two provinces - Battambang and Kampot. The process involves selecting appropriate sites, co-creating interventions, implementing them, expanding the efforts, and evaluating impact.

The purpose of this report is to find suitable locations to implement safety measures in bat guano harvesting communities. During the visit, the focus was on building relationships with local leaders and communities, gathering information about the caves and harvesting process, and identifying committed stakeholders. Suitable sites were chosen based on existing data, discussions with local leaders and government officials. The criteria for site selection included the presence of bats in specific genera (including *Rhinolophus*, *Hipposideros*, and *Mops*), the level of bat-human contact during guano harvest, community willingness to participate in risk reduction interventions, support from the government and partners, and the presence of potential intermediate host species that could facilitate spillover. Interviews, discussions, and observations were used to gather information, with a standardized questionnaire and checklist for interviews and discussions, and an observation matrix for documenting cave observations.

We identified a total of seven mountains with eight bat caves within our target area. Five of these caves are located in Battambang and are home to approximately 11 species of bats, with a combined bat population previously estimated at over 15 million individuals, though some populations may have since decreased. The bat caves are near villages where pigs and goats roam freely, increasing the risk of disease transmission.

Battambang in particular is also home to fruit bats - especially Lyle's flying fox, which has been found to carry Nipah virus. A large roost (>1500 individuals) is located near a pagoda surrounded by densely populated villages and local markets. Though Nipah virus is out of the planned scope of this report, due to its stated importance to government partners, additional work related to fruit bats and the Nipah virus could be considered in the future.

Based on our findings, STOP Spillover Cambodia plans to work directly with the bat guano harvesters in the Phnom Reach Trob cave and Phnom Kuhear Loung cave as the two selected intervention groups, while Phnom Sampov' cave may be used as a control site for evaluation purposes. Other caves were not selected, as they did not meet selection criteria but may indirectly benefit through risk awareness campaigns.

INTRODUCTION

BACKGROUND

Bats live in a wide range of habitats. The primary group of STOP Spillover priority pathogens believed to be associated with cave-dwelling bats in Cambodia are zoonotic coronaviruses. People in Cambodia harvest bat guano from many natural cave sites, and bat guano is sold at good prices, largely for use as fertilizer on high value horticultural crops such as durian and black pepper (Chhay, 2012). Bat guano harvesting creates many opportunities for direct viral transmission through contact with guano or urine, via oral, respiratory, or mucous membrane contact routes. In addition, visitors to caves for religious and cultural purposes, tourism, and incidental use such as storage are also subject to indirect bat contact through guano and urine, though perhaps with a lower intensity and frequency than guano harvesters (Furey et al. 2018; Lim et al. 2018). Bat hunting and consumption, either for food or traditional medicines (Furey et al. 2016) is also a documented exposure pathway and likely creates the closest and most direct form of contact.

With lessons learned from work with bat guano harvesters operating artificial roosts in Kampong Cham province, STOP Spillover Cambodia has begun developing interventions in other bat-human interface sites in Battambang and Kampot provinces. These new interventions will engage people who harvest bat guano from bat caves, to mitigate potential zoonotic spillover risk. The activity will also target bat hunters, tourists, tour operators, and religious leaders. Interventions will be co-designed with target groups and tailored to their needs and capacities.

This activity includes the following steps: (i) site selection and baseline establishment; (ii) intervention co-creation; (iii) implementation; (iv) cross-pollination and expansion; and (v) evaluation and synthesis.

OBJECTIVES

The overall goal of this site selection exercise in Battambang and Kampot province is to determine suitable cave-associated bat guano harvest sites in the provinces of Battambang and Kampot for implementation of community-level risk reduction interventions.

The specific aims of the site visit were to:

- develop relationships and collaboration with concerned provincial departments, district and local leaders and bat guano harvesting communities,
- identify and enroll OH-DReaM Working Group members to work with the project,
- describe the situation, characteristics and geographical location of bat caves,
- solicit information about bat guano harvesting activities, commodity chain processes and relevant risk pathways, and
- identify people and key stakeholders involved in bat guano harvesting activities, and their commitment to collaborating with STOP Spillover.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SITE SELECTION CRITERIA

Using existing data and discussions with local leaders and district and provincial government officials, a set of suitable sites were selected. Site selection criteria included:

- i. Presence of a significant number of bats in the genus *Rhinolophus* (and secondarily, the genera *Hipposideros* and *Mops*),
- ii. Level of opportunity for bat-human contact during bat guano harvest (e.g., number of people involved and their gender and age, frequency, and level of existing protective measures),
- iii. Willingness of community to participate in risk reduction interventions,
- iv. Support of government (including local authorities) and local implementing partners, and
- v. Presence of potential intermediate host species (primarily domestic animals).

The initial shortlist of eligible sites established based on the National Interface Risk Assessment (NIRA; STOP Spillover, March 2023) and site visits included:

- i) Phnom Sampov (Battambang),
- ii) Phnom Ta Kream (Battambang)
- iii) Phnom Reach Trob, (Aka Phnom Rumsay Sak; Battambang),
- iv) Phnom L'ang (Kampot),
- v) Phnom Kourhea Loung (Kampot) and
- vi) Phnom Kampong Trach (Kampot).

Several other potential sites were also identified, but either lacked important data or failed to meet all criteria (e.g., sites where guano harvest has likely ceased due to loss of bat colonies).

PARTICIPATION OF GOVERNMENT INSTITUTIONS

To coordinate participation of the Government of Cambodia's (GOC) institutions in the site selection process, letters were sent to key partner GOC institutions at the national and sub-national levels (Fig. 1). The involvement and participation of GOC institutions is important to get their support and buy-in for STOP Spillover Cambodia's activities and interventions. Not all key partner institutions from the national level were available to join the missions.

Figure 1. Flow of GOC engagement by STOP Spillover

DATA COLLECTION METHODS AND TOOLS

The target interface is the cave bat-human interface in Battambang and Kampot provinces. Potential interface sites and bat cave locations were proposed in STOP Spillover Cambodia’s Year 4 Annual Work Plan and Activity Action Plans. Data to make final decisions on the selection of specific target bat caves was collected using key informant interviews (KIs), focus group discussions (FGDs), and site observations. For KIs and FGDs the same questionnaire and checklist was employed (Annex 1). Data collected from bat cave observations were recorded in a bat cave observation matrix (Annex 2). Data were entered and analyzed in Excel file datasets. All the tools above were developed based on the stakeholders and risk pathway analysis as well as on possibilities of some intervention activities to help the community reduce the risks of zoonotic spillover.

PARTICIPATION OF STAKEHOLDERS

STOP Spillover Cambodia engaged as many representatives of GOC key institutions as possible. However, due to the timing of field missions and GOC staff availability, representatives of certain GOC institutions, specifically from the national level, were not able to participate. Representatives of GOC institutions participated in key portions of the field mission.

GOC institutions that were able to participate in the site selection mission in Battambang and Kampot included officials and/or personnel of the Ministry of Environment (MOE), the Center for Disease Control (CDC) of the Ministry of Health, the Provincial Departments of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (PDAFFs) and Forestry Cantonments (FCs), Provincial Departments of Environment (PDOEs), Provincial Health Departments (PHDs), and district level as well as commune level authorities (Annex 3).

GOC officials, personnel, and stakeholders participating in both Battambang and Kampot missions not only provided very constructive input, but also served as key informants. They were very helpful throughout the process. They were very supportive during all field activities.

KEY INFORMANT INTERVIEWS

Six key informant interviews in both target provinces were conducted. Key informants comprised officials and/or directors of the Provincial Departments of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (PDAFFs), Provincial Health Departments (PHDs), and Provincial Departments of Environment (PDOEs). Three KIIs in Battatambang were administered in which officials from the national level participated. In Kampot province, three KIIs with three district officials were implemented in three different districts where bat caves of interest are situated. A list summarizing final KII can be seen as in Table I. KII candidates were targeted to officials of the at-subnational stakeholders, particularly those who work in PHD, PDOE and PDAFF of two provinces. Selection of focused groups were of those who were at the community levels including local authorities, community leaders and representatives and health centers etc.

Table I. List of KII by Locations in the Two Provinces

No.	Name	Gender	Institutions and Province
1	Sin Sothy	M	PHD, Battambang
2	Duong Piset	M	PDOE, Battambang
3	Rath Sokheang	F	PDAFF, Battambang
4	Touch Sopheary	F	PHD, Kampot
5	Rath Sokheang	F	PDOE, Kampot
6	Sorng Chea	M	PDAFF, Kampot

At each KII meeting, objectives, activities and action plans were shared and formal requests for engagement and participation of concerned departments, authorities and administrations at the sub-national level in STOP Spillover’s activities and interventions were requested.

Altogether, 12 officials/directors of the concerned provincial departments in Battambang and Kampot provinces, and three district officials of concerned districts in Kampot province were involved in the KIIs. KIIs were informative and constructive. Key informants provided necessary information and useful suggestions to the team to select bat caves for potential interventions.

The officials/directors of the provincial departments accompanied the team to the field and facilitated their access to district administrations and communities under their respective

jurisdictions. These officials reaffirmed their commitment to providing all necessary cooperation and assistance to STOP Spillover to implement activities and interventions in the two provinces.

FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSIONS

Focus group discussions (FGDs) were administered at the district level. Representatives of concerned authorities and administrations as well as stakeholders were involved. Three FGDs were executed in Battambang province, in Banan district where all bat caves of interest are located. FGDs engaged 21 representatives of the Banan district administration, commune councils, village authorities, and Romsay Sak and Phnom Phnom Sampov communities (Annex 4). A meeting with seven members of Angkar Bareebo, a Battambang-based NGO that supports bat farming, was also conducted (Annex 5).

In Kampot where bat caves of interest spread in three different districts, three FGDs were conducted. In total, 34 informants participated in the FGDs, including 15 representatives of three target districts (of Kampong Trach, Banteay Meas and Dang Tung), three commune councils (of Damnak Kantuot Khang Tbound, Tuk Meas Khang Lech and L'ang), three village heads (of Phum Damnak Kantuot, Phum Chrockley, Phum L'ang), six representatives of three health centers (of Damnak Kantuot HC, Chhouk OD, Khnach Prey HC), and four representatives of Phnom Kuhear Loung and Phnom L'ang communities (Annex 6). A table summarizing final FGD people interviewed by location as shown in Table 2 below.

In each FGD, the site selection team shared STOP Spillover objectives, activities, and action plans. Both national- and provincial-level officials actively assisted the team facilitating these FGDs, to engage participants in discussions about bat cave-related aspects, activities and issues, and to solicit their commitment to participating in future STOP Spillover activities and interventions.

FGDs focused on bat cave characteristics (geographic location, bat species, and surrounding environment), bat guano related activities (harvesting, packing, relocating, storing, selling, etc.), religious activities in the caves, groups of people involved (ages, sexes, etc.), risk behaviors of those engaged with bat guano related and religious activities, risk preventative measures, NGO/INGO or GOC initiatives related to bats, and willingness of communities and local authorities to collaborate with and participate in STOP Spillover-supported activities and interventions.

Table 2. List of FGDs by Locations in the Two Provinces

No.	FGD' Code	Location	Number of Participants (persons)
I	FGD001- PRSFPC	Phnom Romsay Sak, Banan, Battambang	07

2	FGD002- Sampov	Phnom Sampov, Banan, Battambang	05
3	FGD003- Ta Kream	Phnom Ta Kream, Banan, Battambang	05
4	FGD004- Kampong Trach	Phnom Kampong Trach, Kampot	13
5	FGD005- PKLFPC	Phnom Kuhear Loung, Kampot	12
6	FGD006-L'ang	Phnom L'ang, Kampot	12

BAT CAVE OBSERVATIONS

There are three bat caves in Battambang province. However, given the time and weather conditions, the team was able to conduct an observational visit to only one cave, the eastern cave of Phnom Sampov, in Phnom Sampov commune of Banan district. In Kampot province, three observations were conducted at identified bat caves, which are located on Phnom Kampong Trach, Phnom Kuhear Luong, and Phnom L'ang.

At each cave observations focused on bat guano related activities (bat guano collection, packing, transferring, storing, etc.), use of harvesting equipment and supplies, biosafety and hygiene practices, and surrounding farming and animal raising activities. In Battambang province, the team could not observe any related activities due to unfavorable weather conditions and the visit occurred on the closing day for bat guano collection. The team could only visit bat guano storage facilities and conduct observations of the surrounding environment. Nonetheless, the meeting with leaders/representatives of Phnom Reach Trob, Phnom Sampov and Phnom Ta Kream caves allowed the team to gather needed information and data.

In Kampot province, three bat caves were visited and observed, focusing on the same aspects as in Battambang. Only one cave, in Phnom Kuhear Loung, was in operation on the date visited; the other two were on break. The team observed actual activities in one cave. For the other two caves, the team collected information and data from leaders/representatives of the bat guano harvesters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

BAT CAVE FEATURES

Bat caves have fascinating natural features that provide shelter and habitats for many bat species in Battambang and Kampot. Bat caves are typically found in karst landscapes where limestone rock, which is highly water-soluble, forms underground chambers and passages. Bat caves are important for the ecosystem services that bats provide, such as seed dispersal, pollination, and pest control. Bats can fly long distances from their caves and affect the surrounding landscape (Edson and Enrico, 2021).

Each bat cave in both Battambang and Kampot provinces is located higher up near the top of the mountains. Access to the caves is challenging and dangerous. The team heard anecdotal reports of accidents involving bat guano harvesters while working.

The three bat caves identified in Banan district (Battambang province) where bat guano is harvested are located close to each other (Fig. 2). These caves host mostly the same bat species and their bat colonies are

interconnected (Edson and Enrico, 2021). Bat species can be shared among the nearby caves, and the bat colonies may move from one cave to another because of several factors such as noise and hunting activities (Edson and Enrico, 2021). According to community leaders, a group of two or three people is assigned to guard the cave on Phnom Reach Trob to prevent undesirable activities such as hunting or any attempts to disperse bat colonies using smoke or by making noise.

“Because of community protection, the size of the bat population is increasing in Phnom Reach Trob’s cave” the leader of Phnom Rumsay Sak Forestry Protection Community (PRSFPC) reported. The bat population in caves in Phnom Sampov and Phnom Ta Kream is decreasing due to human disturbances (hunting, tourism, religious rituals, etc.). Bat guano harvesting activities in Phnom Reach Trob’s cave occur only at

Fig. 2: Locations of bat caves of interest in Battambang province

night when bats forage. At other caves, such activities occur during the daytime, disturbing bat colonies.

In Kampot province, the three bat caves of interest are situated far apart from each other in three different districts (Fig. 3). The bat population in Phnom Kuhear Loung and Phnom Kampong Trach remains unchanged, according to community representatives. In 2016, the bat populations

Fig. 3: Locations of bat caves of interest in Kampot province

in Phnom Kampong Trach and Phnom Kuhear Loung caves were recorded, respectively, at less than 1,000 and 0.9 million (Furey et al. 2016). As for the cave on Phnom L'ang, the bat population is declining because of quarrying activities and the use of dynamite at the cement factory.

Allen et al. (2021) confirm this detrimental practice. Bat guano harvesting in Phnom Kuhear Loung's cave collects more bat droppings than in Phnom Lang's cave. The bat guano collectors at Phnom Lang's cave are the same bat guano collectors from Phnom Kuhear Loung; they are hired by a local operator of that cave who received

harvesting rights from the cement factory. In Phnom Kampong Trach, only an elderly lady collects bat guano in order to keep the location clean for tourists and religious activities.

Rural villages are located near all of these caves, where farm animals and pets are raised. These animals are generally allowed to range freely in the area surrounding the caves. Commercial livestock farms were also reported situated in nearby areas. Large commercial pig farms are found near the Phnom Ta Kream cave. Next to the guano warehouse of Phnom Kuhear Loung community is a pen where 40 goats are kept; these goats are allowed to range freely in the area. According to Yang et al. (2021) goats are susceptible to and may be intermediate hosts of SARS-CoV-2, so the potential exists for this species to act as a bridging host to humans for bat-borne coronaviruses.

BAT SPECIES

Cave Bats

Based on KILs, FGDs and existing documents, the team identified 11 bat species that live in caves of interest in Battambang and Kampot provinces. The presence of different bat species and colonies at each cave are described in Table 3. Of the 11 species identified, *Rhinolophus spp.* may be of highest interest for STOP Spillover as coronaviruses previously found in this species are the closest relative to SARS-CoV-2. Deborah et al. (2021) identified coronaviruses in two samples of *Rhinolophus shameli* bats in Cambodia in 2010 that shared 92.6% nucleotide identity with SARS-CoV-2. This species is found in four of the 8 caves in Battambang and Kampot provinces (Table 1).

Photo 1: Goat cage near the Phnom Kuhear cave

Table 3. Cave bat species

No	Cave's names, province	Latitude, Longitude	Bat species recorded	No. of bats (estimated)	No. of guano harvesters (people)
1	Phnom Sampov, Battambang	32.022 N 103.095 E (Eastern cave)*	1. <i>Mops plicatus</i> 2. <i>Taphozous melanopogon</i> 3. <i>Pipistrellus javanicus</i> 4. <i>Rhinolophus shameli</i>	1.8 million**	10*
2	Phnom Sampov, Battambang	13.026 N 103.099 E (Western cave)*	1. <i>Mops plicatus</i>	1 million**	
3	Phnom Reach Trob, Battambang	12.95925 N 103.09827 E*	1. <i>Mops plicatus</i> 2. <i>Taphozous melanopogon</i>	11 million**	20*

No	Cave's names, province	Latitude, Longitude	Bat species recorded	No. of bats (estimated)	No. of guano harvesters (people)
4	Phnom Ta Kream, Battambang	13.066 N 103.051 E*	1. <i>Mops plicatus</i>	800,000**	3*
5	Phnom Khpos (in Ta Kream commune), Battambang	N/A	1. <i>Mops plicatus</i>	200-300**	1*
6	Phnom Kampong Trach, Kampot	10.573184 N 104.470372 E*	1. <i>Mops plicatus</i> , 2. <i>Cynopterus sphinx</i> , 3. <i>Eonytoris spelaea</i> , 4. <i>Hipposideros (grandis, cinemaceus)</i> 5. <i>Hypsugo dolichodon</i> , 6. <i>Megaderma spama</i> , 7. <i>Myotis muricola</i> 8. <i>Rhinolophus (shameli, malayanus)</i> 9. <i>Rousettus leschenaulti</i> 10. <i>Taphozous (longimatus, melanopogon)</i>	>1000**	1*
7	Phnom Kuhear Loung, Kampot	10.662 N 104.538 E*	1. <i>Mops plicatus</i> 2. <i>Cynopterus sphinx</i> 3. <i>Hipposideros (grandis, cineraceus, larvatus, pomona)</i> 4. <i>Megaderma (spama, lyra)</i> 5. <i>Rhinolophus (shameli, malayanus, acuminatus, pusillus)</i> 6. <i>Taphozous (melanopogon)</i>	0.9 million**	25*
8	Phnom La'ang, Kampot	10.714 N 104.339 E*	1. <i>Mops plicatus</i> 2. <i>Hipposideros (larvatus, pomona)</i>	370,000**	7* (Most are the same collectors)

No	Cave's names, province	Latitude, Longitude	Bat species recorded	No. of bats (estimated)	No. of guano harvesters (people)
			3. <i>Rhinolophus (shameli, malayanus)</i> 4. <i>Cynopterus sphinx</i>		from Phnom Kuhear Loung)
Total	7 mountains	8 caves	11 spp.	> 15.0 million	> 60

Sources: *Spillover Cambodia (2023), and ** Furey, N et al., (2016).

Flying Foxes and Nipah Virus

During the field mission, specifically in Battambang province, the team was informed by local stakeholders of the presence of flying foxes or fruit bats and their roosts, which are located within the premises of Bay Damram pagoda. The pagoda is situated in close proximity to densely populated villages and to two local markets, Boeng Chhouk market and Battambang's morning market.

Three species of fruit bats have been identified in Cambodia, including large flying fox *Pteropus vampyrus*, Lyle's flying fox *P. lylei* and island flying fox *P. hypomelanus*; their roosts are spread across multiple sites in the country (Table 2).

Flying foxes, specifically *Pteropus lylei* spp., are reported to host Nipah virus (NiV), which is known to be transmitted to humans and is one of the five zoonotic viruses/diseases high on the GOC's priority list. According to Duong et al. (2021) 1.03% (8/773) of fruit bat urine samples in Battambang were confirmed positive for NiV by RT-PCR. Fruit bats, therefore, should be an additional focus of STOP Spillover Cambodia in year 5. Preliminary work including interface identification and selection should be considered during this fiscal year (Y4).

Table 4. Roost locations, species and population of flying foxes in Cambodia

No.	Location (province)	No. of bats in 2013	Species	Comments
1	Bay Damram pagoda (Battambang)	1400	<i>Pteropus lylei</i> <i>P. vampyrus</i>	Roosts near the market, pig farms, the pagoda, and the river
2	Royal garden (Siem Reap)	5000	<i>Pteropus lylei</i> <i>P.vampyrus</i>	14 roosts in trees in an urban park

No.	Location (province)	No. of bats in 2013	Species	Comments
3	Wat Prek Chey Lech Wat Pi Chey Sakor (Kandal)	500 4000	<i>Pteropus lylei</i> <i>P. vampyrus</i>	Roosts on pagoda compounds; people at risk include bat hunters, palm juice collectors, fruit plantation owners, owners and workers of commercial pig farms
4	PDOE's compound Kampong Thom	6000	<i>Pteropus lylei</i> <i>P. vampyrus</i>	Three roosts in trees on the PDOE's compound, also found in fruit plantations (mango farms, sapodilla farms)
5	Cambodia Development Council's compound (Phnom Penh)	1800	<i>Pteropus lylei</i> <i>P. vampyrus</i>	Tourist attraction
6	Koh Bong Island (Sihanoukville)	200	<i>Pteropus hypomelanus</i>	Three roosts in the forest of a small private island
7	Ang Trapeang Thmor (Banteay Meanchey)	200	<i>Pteropus lylei</i> <i>P. vampyrus</i>	One roost near an irrigation system reservoir
8	Koh Trong island Koh Chreng island (Kratie)	200 900	<i>Pteropus lylei</i>	Two roosts in trees on the pagoda compound on Koh Trong island; 17 roosts in trees on the pagoda compound on Koh Chreng island
9	Wat Srey Santhor (Kampong Cham)	N/A	<i>Pteropus lylei</i> <i>P. vampyrus</i>	Roosts on a pagoda compound
10	Wat Veal Lbang (Prey Veng)	700	<i>Pteropus lylei</i> <i>P. vampyrus</i>	12 roosts in trees near the pagoda
Total	10 sites	> 200,000	3	> 50 roosts

Source: S. Ravon et al., 2014

BAT GUANO SUPPLY CHAIN

BAT GUANO SUPPLY CHAIN ORGANIZATION

Bat guano handling activities in both Battambang and Kampot provinces are quite similar (Annex 7), and are organized in three formats: (a) community based, (b) managed by unregistered private enterprises, and (c) undertaken by individual households.

Community-based bat guano organizations: Two bat guano related community-based organizations are active - one in Battambang province and another in Kampot province. The bat guano community-based organization in Battambang was registered with the Forestry Administration (FA) of the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries (MAFF) in 2014 as Phnom Rumsay Sak Forestry Protection Community (PRSFPC). The community is granted the rights to the management of Phnom Reach Trob's bat cave. The community in Kampot province was registered with the Ministry of Environment (MOE) in 2020 as Phnom Kuhear Loung Forestry Protection Community (PKLFPC), and is under the jurisdiction of PDOE.

Both communities have a well-defined organizational and management structure, and good working relationships with respective provincial departments, and local administrations and authorities. The community leadership works closely with community members, and organizes all aspects of the bat guano supply chain from harvesting to selling. These two communities are also responsible for protecting the caves to which they are granted rights. They are prepared to support and collaborate with STOP Spillover to mitigate the risk of viral spillover from bats to humans.

Phnom Rumsay Sak Forestry Protection Community (PRSFPC) manages the bat guano supply chain at the Phnom Reach Trob bat caves. It has 50 household members. Twenty community members (incl. 10 committee members) are involved in collecting the guano, while three committee members assume the role of guards whose responsibility is to protect bats from hunting or harassment, and to control unfavorable activities near the caves that would disturb the bat colonies. The community does not have enough labor for guano collection; therefore, they hire non-community-member workers from nearby villages to help with guano collection.

Phnom Kuhear Loung Forestry Protection Community (PKLFPC) has 39 member households and is responsible for the bat guano supply chain at Phnom Kuhear Loung. All member households are engaged with bat guano handling activities; 25 of them are bat guano collectors, one is the bat guano packer, three are bat guano fetchers, and 10 are bat guano traders. Unlike members of PRSFPC, PKLFPC member households do not share their sales profit with the community committee. However, they have to pay a fee of 4,000 Riels/30-kg bag to PDOE. Also, there were no clear gender-based patterns identified in the roles between men, women and youth in the supply chain of both groups.

Non-registered private enterprises: There are two unregistered private enterprises dealing in the bat guano commodity chain, one in Battambang province, and another in Kampot province. The one in Battambang province is run by the family of a retired soldier. He inherited the business from his father who covered both western and eastern caves of Phnom Sampov. The family hires around 10 local villagers, who are men only, as workers who gather, pack, and store the bat guano. They are also responsible for bringing the collected guano from caves down to the storage hut where the family operator handles guano sales.

This unregistered private enterprise in Kampot province is managed by an official from Kampot Provincial Department of Mines and Energy (KPDME). The enterprise assumes the whole operation of bat guano related activities of Phnom L'ang bat cave that is situated in a mining concession owned by Thai Boon Roong Cement Co., Ltd. Access to the cave is restricted and controlled through a single entrance by the company. Without permission and facilitation by the

afore-mentioned KPDME official, access to the Phnom L'ang bat cave is not possible. The KPDME official hires 7 men from PKLFPC as his workers for his operation in Phnom L'ang bat cave.

Individual households: At three bat caves, two in Battambang province and another in Kampot province, there are only individual households who deal with the guano commodity chain. They have individual spots in the caves where they harvest guano. These households have been in the guano business for over 20 years. In Battambang province, three families of retired soldiers manage and collect the guano from the Phnom Ta Kream bat cave. A teacher's family manages guano harvesting and selling from another cave, which is located on Phnom Sampov. The teacher's family is also a bat guano trader who purchases the guano from the Phnom Ta Kream bat cave guano harvesters. As for Kampot province, there is only one guano collector who gathers guano from a cave on Phnom Kampong Trach, and she is an elderly Buddhist nun. Her main purpose is to keep the cave clean for religious worshipers and tourists. Her family uses the guano she collects for farming.

GUANO HARVESTING SCHEDULES

Guano harvesting occurs twice a month at all caves, except at those on Phnom Kampong Trach and Phnom Kuhear Loung. At the cave on Phnom Kampong Trach, the elderly nun collects the guano once every 2-3 months, whereas guano is harvested daily at the cave on Phnom Kuhear Loung. According to KILs, guano harvesting occurs year round, and harvest frequency does not vary seasonally.

GUANO HARVESTER DEMOGRAPHICS

Bat guano collectors are 20 - 60 years of age. Most of them (70%) are men; women are a minority. Most of the old harvesters work at the caves on Phnom Ta Kream, Phnom Kampong Trach and Phnom Kuhear Loung. Collecting guano from bat caves is a dangerous livelihood as the caves are situated high up on the mountains and accessing them requires scaling up and down cliffs. These cliffs are usually quite steep.

BIOSAFETY AND HYGIENE PRACTICES IN GUANO HANDLING

There is no difference in awareness of risk and biosafety and hygiene practices among harvesters, workers, traders/buyers and transporters in handling bat guano at all locations. They do not use or wear any PPE such as protective clothes, masks, gloves or boots (Table 3). Nearly all of them work barefoot as it is not easy for them to move up and down the cliffs with footwear on bamboo/wooden ladders. Washing stations are seen at certain places, generally at the foot of the mountains, where harvesters may bathe and/or wash.

At the local level, commune councils have their own development programs financed by commune investment funds (CIFs). The CIFs are supported by both GOC and development partners (donors and NGOs). No CIF programs encountered do any work connected with zoonotic diseases or viral spillover. They are focused solely on local infrastructure development.

STOP Spillover is the only initiative in both Battambang and Kampot provinces addressing viral spillover in cave bat-human interface at the present time.

Table 5. Materials and gears currently used by cave operators and guano harvesters in bat guano handling

No.	Location	Materials and gears currently used	PPE
1	Phnom Sampov	Harvesters wear only shorts, and no footwear. They are given baby powder to apply to their bodies to repel insects, fleas, lice, etc. They bathe after work, but few use soap. All wear the same clothes until they return home.	None
2	Phnom Reach Trob	Harvesters wear T-shirts and trousers, use krama (traditional, light cotton towel/scarf), and sometimes hats to shield themselves from insects. All wear the same clothes after work until they return home.	None
3	Phnom Ta Kream	Harvesters – three elderly men only – wear T-shirts, shorts, and no footwear. They spray insecticide to repel insects, fleas, lice, etc. All wear the same clothes after work until they return home.	None
4	Phnom Kampong Trach	Harvester – an elderly nun – wears home clothes only.	None
5	Phnom Kuhear Loung	Some harvesters apply powder to their heads and faces to repel insects, lice, fleas, etc. They wear long-sleeved shirts and pants. They have a washing station nearby the guano storage facility, but no soap. They bathe in a small pond after work, and wear the same clothes until they get home.	None
6	Phnom L'ang	Same harvesters from Phnom Kuhear Loung above. No washing station.	None

Source: *STOP Spillover (2023)*

Tourists and religious worshipers who visit the caves on Phnom Sampov and Phnom Kampong Trach – well-known tourist attractions and religious sites – do not use any protective equipment and have limited or no awareness of risk according to results from direct observation and an interview with stakeholders. Since the caves are active guano harvesting sites with bat droppings, risk of exposure could be quite high for these groups of people. Fornazari (2021) considered this

as an opportunity for spillover events from bats to humans with new and undiscovered pathogens, especially viruses.

PROJECTS RELATED TO BAT-HUMAN INTERFACES

Several development projects are reported by participants to be active in the two provinces (Table 4). However, only one concerns the bat-human interface. This new project is being planned by Angkar Bareebo organization. The organization will support local communities to construct bat roosts and to collect bat guano for sale.

Table 6. Identified development and research projects in the two provinces

No.	Project name	Objective	Implementing agency
1	HARVEST	Establish Phnom Rumsay Sak Forestry Community to improve management of local forest and community livelihoods.	Ponleu Komar Organization
2	HARVEST	Establish Kamping Pouy Forestry Community to improve management of local forest and community livelihoods.	RECOFT
3	Bat Farming Project	Sustainable income generation through bat farming for guano.	Angkar Boreebo
4	WASH Program	Improve access to clean drinking water and promote WASH at primary schools and healthcare facilities.	World Vision
5	BCOMING	Sampling of both insectivorous and fruit bats in Steung Treng and Battambang provinces, with plans for future modeling and risk reduction work on Coronaviruses and NiV.	CIRAD, IPC, MERFI

Source: *STOP Spillover (2023)*

CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

CONCLUSIONS

In total, 7 mountains with 8 bat caves were identified in the two target provinces; five of the bat caves are located in Battambang. The caves host at least 11 species of bats with a total population estimated to exceed 15 million individuals, though some colonies may have declined in size since estimates were made. Access to the entrance of most caves is dangerous as they are situated near mountain tops. Access to the areas where guano is harvested is even more dangerous, physically, because the cliffs entering them are steep, and only poorly-structured bamboo/wooden ladders are used to access them.

Besides the cave bats, the team learned that in Battambang there are flying foxes (or fruit bats) with a total population estimated at about 1,400. One of the two fruit bat species is Lyle's flying fox (*Pteropus lylei*), which has been detected as a host of NiV – a virus transmissible to humans with high case fatality (Reynes et al 2005). Several roost trees are reported to be in the compound of Bay Damram pagoda, which is located near two local markets and surrounded by densely populated villages.

All of the bat caves of interest to STOP Spillover are located close to populated villages. Livestock are reported to range freely near these caves and pig and goat farms are also found in their vicinity. This could present opportunities for risk spillover events via animal bridging hosts. The bat species present in these areas include *Rhinolophus shameli* – a species from which one of the closest relatives (92.6% of its nucleotide identity) to SARS-CoV-2 has been detected. Pigs, interestingly enough, appear not to be susceptible either to SARS-CoV (Weingartl et al 2004) or SARS-CoV-2 infection (Meekins et al 2020), but played a well-documented and critical role as bridging hosts between flying foxes and humans in the initial Malaysian Nipah Virus outbreak (Chua et al 1999). Goats can be infected with SARS-CoV-2, although they produce relatively low viral titers (Fernandez-Bastit et al 2022). The high host competence of white-tailed deer for SARS-CoV-2 (Hale et al 2022) underlines the potential for ruminants to serve as important hosts for SARS-like coronaviruses.

Altogether, at least 60 people live off bat guano collection at these eight caves; most of those are connected with the caves on Phnom Kuhear Loung (25 pers.), Phnom Reach Trob (20 pers.) and Phnom Sampov (10 pers.). All of the guano collectors and others who handle the guano – guano traders and transporters – do not use any protective equipment. Although washing stations are available at some sites, soap is not commonly used, and guano harvesters do not change out of their working clothes or gear after work, nor after their bath *in situ*; they change their clothes only once they get home, enabling a potential take-home pathway for any contamination present.

The caves on two mountains – Phnom Sampov in Battambang province and Phnom L’ang in Kampot province – are privately operated and managed. The family that runs the Phnom Sampov’s two bat caves employs 10 bat guano harvesters and is open and very cooperative. The firm that manages Phnom L’ang’s bat cave is secretive and rather difficult to access. However, most or all of the guano harvesters employed there are the same individuals from the Phnom Kuhear Loung cave. Thus, interventions targeting Phnom Kuhear Loung’s bat caves may benefit guano harvesters at Phnom L’ang.

NEXT STEPS

Based on these findings, STOP Spillover Cambodia will directly work with bat guano harvesters in the Phnom Reach Trob cave and Phnom Kuhear Loung cave, and their communities (PRSFPC and PKLFPC). Guano harvesters at other caves will benefit indirectly through risk awareness campaigns, and some may be able to serve as control groups for evaluation purposes. A summary of selected sites is provided in Table 7 . Preliminary basic work related to fruit bats and NiV should be considered, based on the supportive views of local government partners. Subsequent actions are planned as follows:

BAT CAVES

- Conduct community consultative dialogues to (a) establish appropriate baseline data, and (b) co-design risk reduction interventions,
- Implement risk reduction interventions,
- Monitor and evaluate risk reduction interventions, and
- Scale up successful risk reduction interventions to additional sites.

Table 7. A Summary of specific sites selected

No.	Site	Selection Purpose
1	PRSFPC, Banan, Battambang	Intervention site
2	PKLFPC, Banteay Meas, Kampot	Intervention site
3	Phnom Sampov Bat Cave, Battambang	Possible control site or intervention site

FRUIT BATS AND NiV

- Submit a work plan amendment to USAID for approval
- Conduct interface identification and selection (including target provinces), and
- Develop a concept note and action plan for activities and interventions.

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ANNEXES

ANNEX I. KII QUESTIONNAIRE AND CHECKLIST

STOP Spillover Cambodia

Activity 2.2.2.3: Community-level Risk Reduction Interventions in Kampot and Battambang provinces

Key Informant Interview

Behavior Risk Reduction and Social Behavior Change

Type of Key informant interview	<input type="checkbox"/> PDAFF <input type="checkbox"/> POE <input type="checkbox"/> PHD <input type="checkbox"/> District Authority <input type="checkbox"/> Commune Council <input type="checkbox"/> Community	Date
		Time (Start-End)
Village		Commune	
District		Province	
Mountain Name			

No.	Variable description/Question	Answers:
1	Serial number (of instrument)
2	Name of bat cave visited
3	Bat species present in the cave
4	Name of the village where the bat cave is situated
5	Name of the commune where the bat cave is situated
6	Name of the district where the bat cave is situated
7	Name of the province where the bat cave is situated
8	Number of surrounding villages

	
9	Number of surrounding communes
10	Household population in all villages surrounding the bat cave visited
11	Does the cave have any bat guano harvesters?
12	Are the bat guano harvesters working as individuals?
13	Are the bat guano harvesters working as community?
14	Are the bat guano harvesters working for any company?
15	Name of community/company
16	Name of agency with which community/company has its registration
17	Number of member households of the community (even if it is not bat guano community)
18	Number of bat guano harvesting households benefiting from the cave
19	Number of bat guano harvesters working on the bat cave
20	Number of female bat guano harvesters working for company
21	Number of male bat guano harvesters working for company
22	Age range of female bat guano harvesters
23	Age range of male bat guano harvesters

24	Do bat guano harvesters use any protective equipment? (If YES, list all PPEs they use)
25	Do bat guano harvesters practice any protective measures?
26	Which months do bat harvesting take place?
27	How often do a harvester harvest the bat guano?
28	How many times per day do a harvester harvest the bat guano?
29	How many days per week do a harvester harvest the bat guano?
30	How many weeks per month do a harvester harvest the bat guano?
31	How many traders are engaged in bat guano transaction?

32	Number of female traders
33	Number of male traders
34	Where do the traders come from?
35	Where do the traders sell the bat guano?
36	How many transporters are involved in the bat guano transaction?
37	Number of female transporters
38	Number of male transporters
39	Are there any visitors to the bat cave?
40	Where are they from?
41	Which months do they visit the cave?
42	Do people observe any religious activities at the cave? (If YES, list activities)
43	Where are they from?
44	Which months do they observe these religious activities?

45	Are there any bat hunting?
46	What are they hunting bats for?
47	Where are they from?
48	Who are they?
49	Which months do they do bat hunting?
50	Is there any Government-supported bat-related projects? (If YES, list all activities/interventions)
51	Is there any Non-government-organization-supported bat-related projects? (If Yes, list all activities/interventions)
52	Is there any livestock grazing/scavenging in or near the bat cave?
53	Is there any pets grazing/scavenging in or near the bat cave?
54	Is there any livestock farm near the bat cave?

ANNEX 2. OBSERVATION MATRIX/TOOLS

STOP Spillover Cambodia

Activity 2.2.2.3: Community-level Risk Reduction Interventions in Kampot and Battambang provinces

Bat Cave Observation Matrix

Behavior Risk Reduction and Social Behavior Change

Instructions:

- This matrix can be used during site visit/selection fieldwork or at the time when community dialogue is conducted.
- Enumerators should conduct observation of bat guano harvesting activities at bat cave only if accessibility presents no risk and danger to their personal safety.
- Record information/data and write down notes from your observations or what you see in the provided blank cells.

Administration				
Mountain name		Community Name (w/ GIS coordinates)		
Enumerator's name		Date	Time (Start-End)	
Village		Commune	District	

No.	Description	Notes			
O.1	Bat cave condition				
O.1.1	Location (direction) and distance (km) of bat cave to communities (sketch a map using a separate sheet of paper and give GIS coordinates)			
O.1.2	Number of entries to bat cave (also give description)			
O.2	Bat guano harvesting activities				
O.2.1	Number of bat guano harvester in the cave	Men	Women	Boys	Girls
O.2.2	Number of bat guano harvester using PPE	Women			
		Item		Number of persons	

		7. Head nets	
		8. Farming hats	
		9. Boots	
		99. Others	
O.2.3	Bat guano harvester activities in the bat cave	
O.2.4	Tools and equipment used in bat guano harvesting activities	
O.2.5	Disposition of PPE after use by:	Men: Women: Boys: Girls:	
O.2.6	Water station for hygiene practices (write also whether soap is used or not and note different practices by sex, if any)	Handwashing:	

		Bathing: PPE washing: Tools and equipment:			
O.2.7	Eating and drinking at bat cave			
O.2.8	Bat guano storage after collection from the cave			
O.3	Bat guano sales activities				
O.3.1	Bat guano sale activities			
O.3.2	Number of people involved in bat guano sales	Men	Women	Boys	Girls

O.3.3	Number of people use PPE while handling bat guano sale activities	<p>Women</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Item</th> <th>Number of persons</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>1. Face mask</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>2. Disposable clothes</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>3. Raincoats</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>4. Gloves</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>5. Washable closed toe shoes</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>6. Face shield</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>7. Head nets</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>8. Farming hats</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>9. Boots</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>99. Others</td><td></td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Men</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Item</th> <th>Number of persons</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>1. Face mask</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>2. Disposable clothes</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>3. Raincoats</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>4. Gloves</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>5. Washable closed toe shoes</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>6. Face shield</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>7. Head nets</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>8. Farming hats</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>9. Boots</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>99. Others</td><td></td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Girls</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Item</th> <th>Number of persons</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>1. Face mask</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>2. Disposable clothes</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>3. Raincoats</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>4. Gloves</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>5. Washable closed toe shoes</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>6. Face shield</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>7. Head nets</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>8. Farming hats</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>9. Boots</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>99. Others</td><td></td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Boys</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Item</th> <th>Number of persons</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>1. Face mask</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>2. Disposable clothes</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>3. Raincoats</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>4. Gloves</td><td></td></tr> </tbody> </table>	Item	Number of persons	1. Face mask		2. Disposable clothes		3. Raincoats		4. Gloves		5. Washable closed toe shoes		6. Face shield		7. Head nets		8. Farming hats		9. Boots		99. Others		Item	Number of persons	1. Face mask		2. Disposable clothes		3. Raincoats		4. Gloves		5. Washable closed toe shoes		6. Face shield		7. Head nets		8. Farming hats		9. Boots		99. Others		Item	Number of persons	1. Face mask		2. Disposable clothes		3. Raincoats		4. Gloves		5. Washable closed toe shoes		6. Face shield		7. Head nets		8. Farming hats		9. Boots		99. Others		Item	Number of persons	1. Face mask		2. Disposable clothes		3. Raincoats		4. Gloves	
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		99. Others	
O.3.4	Tools and equipment used in bat guano sale activities	
O.3.5	Disposition of PPE after use by:	Men: Women: Boys: Girls:	
O.3.6	Water station for hygiene practices (write also whether soap is used or not and note different practices by sex, if any)	Handwashing: Bathing:	

		<p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>PPE washing:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>Tools and equipment:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>
O.3.7	Eating and drinking at sale point	<p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>

O.4. Additional observations

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ANNEX 3. LIST OF GOC PERSONNEL INVOLVED

No	Name	Gender	Government Stakeholders	Date of participation
			National Level	
			Ministry of Health	
1	Chhieb Sunheng	M	Head of Office	23 – 26 October 2023
2	Heng Svannary	F	Public Official	30 Oct – 03 Nov 2023
			Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries (MAFF)	
3	None	None	NA	NA
			MAFF – Forestry Administration (FA)	
4	None	None	NA	NA
			Ministry of Environment (MoE)	
5	Sun Bora	M	Head of Office	30 Oct – 03 Nov 2023
			Regional/Provincial Level	
			Provincial Dept of Environment (PDoE)	
6	Eng Polo	M	Head of Department, KP	01 November 2023
7	Chhim Meng	M	Deputy Head of Office, KP	01 – 03 November 2023
8	Mao Naroath	M	Head of Office, KP	01 November 2023
9	Eoung Hokmeng	M	Contract Official, KP	01 November 2023
10	Doung Piseth	M	Head of Office, BBT	24 – 26 October 2023
			Provincial Depts of Agriculture, Forestry, and fisheries (PDAFF)	
11	Mak Vanny	M	Head of Triange FA Levels, BBT	24 – 26 October 2023

No	Name	Gender	Government Stakeholders	Date of participation
			National Level	
			Ministry of Health	
12	Chek Chanly	M	Head of office, agriculture and animal health, KP	01 November 2023
13	Rath Sokheang	F	Official, Office agriculture and animal health, KP	01 November 2023
14	Nob Savat	M	Official, Office agriculture and animal health, KP	02 November 2023
15	Prum Heng	M	Vice-chief, Agriculture Office, KP	02 November 2023
16	Meas So Met	M	Vice-chief, Agriculture Office, KP	03 November 2023
17	Uy Vanna	M	Deputy Head of Division FA Levels, BBT	25 – 26 October 2023
18	It Thy	M	Head of Triange FA Levels, KP	02 November 2023
19	Seang Sao Thorn	M	Head of Triange FA Levels, KP	03 November 2023
20	Sorng Chea	M	Deputy Head of Division FA Levels, KP	01 – 03 November 2023
			Provincial Depts of Health (PDOH)	
21	Heng Chantha	M	Head of Department, KP	01 – 02 November 2023
22	Touch Sopheary	F	Official, RRT, KP	01 – 03 November 2023
23	Sin Sothy	M	Official, RRT, BBT	24 – 26 October 2023
24			District Levels	
25	Pin Seyha	M	Vice-governor, Kampong Trach, KP	01 November 2023
26	Samrith Sopheana	F	Vice-governor, Banteay Meas, KP	02 November 2023
27	Dol Ry	M	Vice-governor, Dang Tung, KP	03 November 2023
28	Noun Phirum	F	Vice-governor, banan, BBT	24 October 2023
29			Commune Councils	

No	Name	Gender	Government Stakeholders	Date of participation
			National Level	
			Ministry of Health	
30	Em Chan	M	Council, Dang Tung, KP	03 November 2023
31	Sorn Horn	M	Commune Chief, Dang Tung, KP	03 November 2023
32	Bic Boeun	M	Commune Chief, Phnom Sampov, BBT	24 October 2023

ANNEX 4. LIST OF FIELDWORK PARTICIPANTS IN BATTAMBANG PROVINCE

No	Name	Sex	Position	Institution
1	Chhieb Sunheng	M	Officer	CDC
2	Uy Vanna	M	Officer for Forestry	PDAFF
3	Sin Sothy	M	Officer	PHD
4	Duong Piset	M	Officer	PDOE
5	Mak Vanny	M	Vice Head	Forestry Office of PDAFF
6	Noun Phirum	F	Deputy Governor	Banan District Authority
7	Horn Viroth	M	Administrative head	Banan District Authority
8	Chheng Nang	M	Officer of social affair	Banan District Authority
9	Morn Vin	M	Officer of agriculture	Banan District Authority
10	Bic Boeun	M	Commune Chief	Phnom Sampov Commune
11	Ry Chhom	F	Member of women and children committee	Chheu Teal Commune
12	Phouk Kim Yi	M	Head	Takream Health Center
13	Thagn KimKhiet	M	Head	Chheu Teal Health Center
14	Eu Phallin	M	Head	Phnom Sampov Health Center

No	Name	Sex	Position	Institution
15	Thoung Chhoeun	M	Village chief	Sampov Lech Village
16	Ngourn La	M	Vice village chief	Village authority
17	Chao Chhoeun	M	Village chief	Thkov village
18	Roeun Savorn	M	Member	Community
19	Vann Chamnar	M	Member of CC	Takream Commune Authority
20	Lon Bunleoung	M	Community head	Phnom Romsaysak Community
21	Duong Hourm	M	Vice Head	Phnom Romsaysak Community

ANNEX 5. LIST OF MEETINGS WITH NGOS AND OTHER AGENCIES

No	Name	Gender	NGO/ Other agencies	Date of participation
1	David Emery	M	International Director, Bareebo	24 October 2023
2	Kov Bong	M	Local Director, Bareebo	24 October 2023
3	Keo Borany	F	NGO Staff	24 October 2023
4	Chum Chhern	M	NGO Staff	24 October 2023
5	Da Vibol	M	NGO Staff	24 October 2023
6	Rath Sotheary	F	NGO Staff	24 October 2023
7	Eam Vanna	M	NGO Staff	24 October 2023

ANNEX 6. LIST OF FIELDWORK PARTICIPANTS IN KAMPOT PROVINCE

No	Name	Sex	Position	Institution
1	Sun Bora	M	Chief office	MOE
2	Heng Svannary	F	Public official	CDC, MOH
3	Eng Polo	M	Head of PDOE	PDOE
4	Chhim Meng	M	Vice-chief office	PDOE
5	Mao Naroath	M	Vice-chief office	PDOE
6	Eoung Hokmeng	M	Public official	PDOE
7	Pin Seyha	M	Deputy District Governor	Kampong Trach District Hall
8	Sorng Chea	M	Deputy Head of Division FA Levels	PDAFF
9	Din Kunthea	M	Head of Triange FA Levels	PDAFF
10	Chey Sivitou	M	Head of HC	PDH
11	Srey Sann	M	Commune Chief	Damnak Kantout Khang Tboung
12	Hoem Sokphearum	M	Deputy head of Admin Office	Kampong Trach District Hall
13	Chek Chanly	F	Head of office, agriculture and animal health	Kampong Trach District
14	Rath Sokheang	F	Official, Office agriculture and animal health	Kampong Trach District

No	Name	Sex	Position	Institution
15	Nob Savat	M	Official, Office agriculture and animal health	Kampong Trach District
16	Pok Pisey	M	Chief, HC	Damnak Kantout
17	Toch Sopheary	F	Official, RRT	PHD
18	Samrith Sopheana	F	Deputy Governor	Banteay Meas District
19	Pen monyreak	F	Vice chief, HC	Banteay Meas
20	Chey Puth	M	Village Chief	Chrockhley
21	Koeum Neurn	M	First Assistant, Commune	Touk Meas Khang Lech
22	Pa Bopha Phal	F	Vice chief, Admin office	Banteay Meas District
23	Prum Heng	M	Vice-chief, Agriculture office	Banteay Meas District
24	It Thy	M	Head of Triange FA Levels	Bantheay Meas
25	Heng Chantha	M	Head of RRT	PHD
26	Dol Ry	M	Deputy District Governor	Dang Tung District
27	Pa Bona	M	Chief, Admin Office	Dang Tung District
28	Seang Sao Thorn	M	Head of Triange FA Levels	Dang Tung
29	Ouk Vann	M	OD official	Chhouk District

No	Name	Sex	Position	Institution
30	Meas So Met	M	Vice-chief, Agriculture office	Dang Tung
31	King Sreyneth	F	Official, HC	Khnach Prey
32	Sorn Horn	M	Commune Chief	L'ang Commune
33	Muth Phalla	M	Village Chief	L'ang Village
34	Em Chan	M	Commune Council	L'ang Commune
35	Yi Sokun	M	First Assistant, Commune	L'ang Commune
36	Kuy Dina	F	Contract Official	PDOE
37	Leng Sovankanika	F	Contract Official	PDOE
38	Eang Mao	M	Contract Official	PDOE

ANNEX 7. SUMMARY OF BAT GUANO COLLECTION DETAILS

No.	Sites	Packing	Storing	Selling	Remarks
1	Phnom Reach Trob	Outside, just near the cave's entrance.	In a warehouse, which is approx. 700-800m away from the cave.	3 fertilizer companies come to buy and load guano sacks at the warehouse.	Having a group who only change the sacks, and seals.
2	Phnom Sampov	Inside the cave	In a warehouse, which is about 200-300 m down directly from the cave entrance.	Clients or transporters rented by clients come and pick up the guano directly at the warehouse.	Sliding down the guano sacks from the cave's entrance to the warehouse.
3	Phnom Ta Kream	At their houses in the village	At their house	Clients pick up the guano from harvesters' houses in the village.	
4	Phnom Kuhear Loung	In the community warehouse	At the trader houses in the villages	Pick up at the traders' houses in the village	
5	Kampong Trach	At a harvester' house in the village	At her house	Clients loading the guano at her house.	An elderly woman only handles the harvest practice.

No.	Sites	Packing	Storing	Selling	Remarks
6	L'ang	Outside the cave, near the front entrance of the cave.	No storing, collecting, packing then loading for sale done consecutively.	Clients were contacted for picking up the guano immediately after packing at the cave's entrance.	

ANNEX 8. ADDITIONAL PHOTOS

PHOTO 2: STOP Spillover team and GOC officers from national and provincial levels met with Angkar Bareebo, an NGO, during site selection mission in Battambang

PHOTO 3: STOP Spillover Cambodia team and GOC personnel from national and provincial levels met with Rumsay Sak Community Forestry’s representatives during site selection mission in Battambang

PHOTO 4: Phnom Sampov bat cave in Battambang where bat guano collectors harvest guano for their livelihoods

PHOTO 5: STOP Spillover Cambodia team and GOC personnel from national and provincial levels met with Banteay Meas District’s deputy governor and their personnel.

PHOTO 6: Hired workers carry sacks of bat guano at Phnom Kuhear Loung, Banteay Meas district, Kampot Province

PHOTO 7: A typical community bat guano warehouse (Phnom Kuhear Loung).

PHOTO 8: Bat guano harvesters measuring and stuffing bat guano into sacks for traders.